

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN ACTIVATING THE ABILITY TO SEARCH IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Jabborova Marifat Kadiraliyevna

Teacher of the Department of Social and Humanities,
P.F.F.D., (PhD)

Fergana State University.

Fergana, Uzbekistan

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Annotation. One of the important tasks of preparing preschool children for school is preparing the child for literacy in kindergarten and in the family. Future teachers of a preschool educational organization have a special influence on the development of the child's personality, since they contribute to the implementation of the child's creative development and self-improvement.

Key words: complex, individuality, information communication, innovation, gene pool, interactive, principle, function.

Аннотация. Одной из важных задач подготовки детей дошкольного возраста к школьному обучению является подготовка ребенка к грамотности в детском саду и в семье. Будущие воспитатели дошкольной образовательной организации оказывают особое влияние на развитие личности ребенка, поскольку способствуют реализации творческого развития ребенка и его самосовершенствованию.

Ключевые слова: комплекс, индивидуальность, информационная коммуникация, инновация, генофонд, интерактив, принцип, функция.

Introduction. Currently, the demands of the society, especially the family, for a specialist who knows how to organize a pedagogical process taking into account the laws of development of a preschool child, his gender, age and individual characteristics are increasing. Taking this into account, in the past period, a number of regulatory and legal documents aimed at the development of preschool education and effective activity were adopted and comprehensive measures were implemented.

Also, in the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 27, 2020 "On measures to develop the field of pedagogical education in Ukraine" No. It was defined as an important task: the training of professional pedagogic personnel who have thoroughly mastered education and teaching methods, information communication technologies and foreign languages, and have the skills to use modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process; to identify those who are interested in the pedagogical profession and to implement a continuous system of their targeted training and education; improvement of curricula and programs for educational directions and specialties of the field of pedagogical education based on advanced foreign experience, implementation of innovative teaching and learning resources and implementation; improving the quality of education by ensuring the integration of education, science and production in the field, training competitive personnel, effective organization of scientific and innovative activities, etc.

The main part. One of the important tasks in preparing children of preschool age for school education is to prepare the child for literacy in the kindergarten and in the family. In recent years, in our republic, the moral image, scientific potential, development of science and innovation, improvement of the continuous education system, increasing the possibilities of quality education services, and the preparation of highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market have been created in our republic. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev said, "No matter what field we choose, we cannot achieve any changes or a prosperous life without educating modern mature personnel. Preparation of such personnel for a healthy gene pool of the nation begins first of all with the preschool education system. as noted, education of an all-around mature person remains one of the urgent issues facing our society today. The young generation sitting in the school seats today are our successors who will take our work from our hands tomorrow, continue our life and pass it on to the next generation, the owners of the great future of Uzbekistan!

For this reason, the President of the whole country is paying attention to the education of the young generation. Today, the interest in using interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is growing day by day. This method teaches children to search for ready-made knowledge by themselves, to study and analyze independently, and even to draw conclusions by themselves. In this process, the teacher-educator creates conditions for the development, formation, education and upbringing of the individual. At the same time, it performs the function of management and orientation. In the process of education, the child becomes the main figure.

The content of the concept of development of the preschool education system until 2030 is aimed at solving the problem of providing equal initial opportunities for preschool children to enter school.

The future educators of the preschool educational organization have a special impact on the development of the child's personality, because they contribute to the realization of the child's creative development and self-improvement. Accordingly, it is recommended to focus future educators' attention on the following principles of working with children:

- focus on the systematicity of the educational content and the organization of the curriculum;
- extensive use of interactive methods that activate children's inquisitiveness;
- forming a children's team, etc.

The interactive lesson process should be organized in such a way that all children in the group should be active, that is, in the course of the activity, a certain part of the educational materials will be studied independently by the children, and then a comprehensive discussion will be held. Educator pedagogue is the organizer, leader, supervisor of the educational process. The child should feel free in the group and the educational activity should satisfy him from an emotional point of view, only then he can express his thoughts freely. Interactive methods are diverse, and the choice of which method depends on the teacher's current topic, the goals and tasks of the activity topic.

Interactive training is a training in which the teacher and children actively participate, a process that takes place in cooperation.

The use of interactive methods in educational activities unintentionally turns into a psychological game or competition, encouraging even the weak and lazy children to express

their opinions to the general public, not being indifferent to debates, encourages active participation. The right choice of methods used to activate children during the activity and the clear formulation of questions will have a great effect. For this, the goal set for the subject should be clearly defined in the activities, and the way and method of achieving this goal should be carefully considered. Therefore, the educator should be able to foresee what each interactive method will give to the children and organize the educational activity correctly.

When using interactive tools, it is advisable to pay attention to the following.

1. Making sure that children have the knowledge, skills, and abilities related to the subject to complete the tasks given during the activity.
2. To pay attention to the fact that weak children and children with strong knowledge are equal in the group.
3. Ignore noise during group study or discussion.
4. To pay attention to the work of each group, to help if necessary.
5. Encourage and welcome independent thoughts and ideas.
6. Always give clear and understandable instructions to groups. Prepare an additional task for the group that completed the task quickly.
7. Observing them while working in groups, listening to their answers to questions. Trying to attract passive students to the topic by making them interesting.

Conclusion. In short, the interactive method helps to discuss problematic situations on the topics discussed in the group, and to find their solution through debate.

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